

Pioneering photonic solutions: LioniX International's TriPlex™ technology empowers European innovation in photonics

Best practice category

New impetus for chip design, Strengthening manufacturing capacities, Partner collaboration

Stakeholder group

SMEs and start-ups

Value chain position

Chip Design, Fabrication

General Information

LioniX International is a global provider of customised microsystems specialising in photonic integrated circuit modules and custom MEMS (micro-electromechanical systems). Founded in Enschede and headquartered at the University of Twente in the Netherlands, LioniX International has cemented its position as a leader in photonic ICs, with their vertically integrated approach enabling their customers to receive support throughout the whole development cycle. LioniX International's MEMS foundry provides customised solutions, with standard processes which are modifiable according to the customers' specifications. Furthermore, LioniX International is renowned for its unique TriPleX™ technology, a versatile platform that integrates multiple photonic functionalities on a single chip, offering unparalleled performance in a compact footprint.

The company's wide portfolio of patents and a strong presence in high-tech sectors such as telecom, datacom, sensing, and biomedical applications has been enabled by its unwavering commitment to R&D. This explains why, besides its own technical advancements, LioniX also regularly collaborates with its industry partners through a number of EU-funded projects. These projects cover a diverse array of applications (from cancer detection to industrial network enhancements) and help to unlock the full potential of synergies between the collaborating partners. Therefore, LioniX International is recognised in this list for setting Best Practices in New impetus for chip design, Strengthening manufacturing capacities and Partner collaboration.

Activities and best practices

Firstly, LioniX International is highlighted for its TriPleX™ patent pool, a silicon nitride waveguide technology which includes more than 40 patents related to photonic integrated circuits (PICs). This extensive IP collection underpins their market-leading offerings in areas such as bio photonics, telecommunications, and quantum computing, enabling highly sophisticated optical chips with reduced losses and improved reliability. Created over 20 years ago, TriPleX™ has evolved into a mature and stable silicon nitride waveguide technology characterised by extremely low propagation losses, making it ideal for applications across a broad wavelength band from 405 nm to 2350 nm.

Furthermore, LioniX International specialises in custom MEMS development and manufacturing – their philosophy can be summarised as there being “no two MEMS alike.”

The company relies on decades of manufacturing experience to inform its MEMS fabrication process, working with the client to successfully co-develop a MEMS product. This process involves an optional feasibility study, as well as a custom process development phase (to short loop the manufacturing process), prototyping, an engineering run and the final stage production. These exist either as a standalone service or as part of outsourcing of an existing manufacturing flow.

Finally, LioniX International has been actively involved in several cutting-edge R&D projects that highlight their innovative approaches and collaborative spirit within the photonic technology sector. Here's an overview of some of their key collaborations and projects:

- **SPRINTER:** This project aims to transform industrial networks by developing low-cost, energy-efficient, and ultra-dynamic optical transceivers and optical switching solutions. These advancements are intended to support high-capacity connectivity and real-time, reliable communication across industrial settings. LioniX's role involves the design and fabrication of TriPleX® chips that are critical for the project's success, focusing on the integration of tunable external cavity lasers and optical beamforming networks.
- **LOLIPOP:** In this project, LioniX is integrating a variety of materials with its TriPleX® platform to enhance photonic device capabilities. Materials such as lithium niobate, germanium photodiodes, and gallium arsenide are being explored for their light modulation, detection, and emission properties, respectively. The project aims to create new prototypes that demonstrate the potential of these integrated materials in various applications, enhancing functionalities like laser doppler vibrometry and optical squeezing sources.
- **TERA6G:** This project addresses the need for high-capacity data transmission in densely populated areas by developing terahertz integrated systems for 6G networks. LioniX contributes its expertise in low-loss silicon nitride waveguides and integrated microwave photonics to realise scalable arrays of wavelength-tunable lasers and optical beamforming networks essential for ultra-massive MIMO wireless networks.
- **REAP:** LioniX leverages its capabilities in designing and manufacturing photonic integrated circuits to develop new cancer detection technologies that target drug tolerant persister (DTP) cells. The company's contribution to the project involves the development of high-speed tunable laser sources to be used in the photoacoustic microscopy and tomography systems.

Challenges addressed with this practice

LioniX International is spearheading advancements in semiconductor materials to meet the rapidly evolving demands of the technology sector. By focusing on the development of innovative materials and integration technologies, the company is addressing key challenges in the industry such as the need for higher efficiency, lower energy consumption, and greater miniaturisation of semiconductor devices. Through its contributions to the field, LioniX International is not only enhancing the performance and capabilities of semiconductor technologies but also supporting the industry's move towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions. The company's work in developing advanced semiconductor materials is crucial for ensuring the long-term growth and competitiveness of the global technology sector.